

Role of job Performance on the Job Satisfaction: A Study on the Elementary School Teachers

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Abstract: This study examines the relationship between job performance and job satisfaction among elementary school teachers. Job satisfaction is crucial for employee well-being and organizational effectiveness, particularly in educational settings where teacher retention and performance directly impact student outcomes. Descriptive Survey research design has been applied in the current study. Population for the current study comprised of the Elementary school teachers working the district of Paschim Medinipur, West Bengal. Out of the existing population the researcher has selected a sample of 150 elementary school teachers by following the purposive sampling method for collecting the primary data. A teacher made job performance scale was developed to measure the performance level of the respondents on their respective jobs. Another structured questionnaire consisting of 20 statements was used for measuring the job satisfaction level of the Elementary school teachers. Collected data were tabulated and analyzed in the SPSS version 20 by applying the descriptive statistics and ANNOVA and Pearson Correlation Coefficient. The findings reveal that there is a weak positive relationship between job satisfaction and job performance and the job satisfaction has significant impact on the job performance.

Key points: Job Opportunities, Employees, Job Satisfaction, Efficient Performance, Productivity.

Introduction: A person's job is a crucial part of their life. Their employment determines how they live and who they hang out with. Having a happy staff is crucial for any organization. In modern times, the private sector has become an important engine for Pakistan's economic growth. In addition to offering valuable services, they are also giving a lot of individuals a chance to find work. The current research aims to learn how employee work happiness relates to their level of performance, with a focus on the private sector's societal contributions and the importance of job satisfaction in boosting employee performance. - AIt is well recognised that an organization's success and productivity are directly correlated to the level of job satisfaction its workers feel in their work. In order to achieve this goal, academics have analysed work satisfaction from several angles, determining its relative value and how it relates to productivity and performance. The term "job satisfaction" refers to the degree to which an employee enjoys and feels fulfilled by his or her work. Thus, among the many areas of organisational psychology, work satisfaction has attracted the greatest amount of attention and study. Job satisfaction, in Locke's view, is the pleasant emotion that arises from reflecting on and making the most of one's work.

Review of Literature:

Wasaf Inayat (2021) wanted to find out how happy workers were with their jobs and how it affected their productivity in the private sector in Peshawar, Pakistan. In order to achieve this goal, a total of 180 workers were chosen at random from various private organizations in Peshawar. The three kinds of organizations that participated in the study—hospitals, banks, and universities—were each represented by an equal number of workers (n = 60) chosen at random. Research tools included a self-constructed Performance Evaluation version (PRF) and a Minnesota Satisfaction Questionnaire (MSQ-short version) created by Weiss et al. (1967). In order to determine the scales' significance, the reliability statistics of both instruments were computed first. The research found

that there is a substantial association between work satisfaction and the kind of profession. It was also proven that there is a favourable association between work happiness and employee performance. - A According to the survey, workers who were happy with their job performed better than those who were unhappy, which had a positive impact on their organizations. Given the uncertain political and economic climate in Peshawar, it is critical for all businesses to find ways to inspire their workers to give their all, regardless of the tactics they use.

Szymon T. Dziuba et al., (2020) stated that Job satisfaction has a big impact on how an employee performs his job. Both elements have an impact on job safety and employee perception of it. A satisfied employee devotes himself to work, performs orders better, cares for others and for himself. He feels safe in the enterprise. The aim of the paper was to assess employees' job satisfaction and their work performance with use of simply survey. In order to achieve this aim, a survey was conducted among employees of a chosen metallurgical enterprise who were asked to assess level of their job satisfaction. The employees defined their job satisfaction by referring to 20 statements describing this satisfaction and evaluating three factors that were used to compute the satisfaction index. The survey allowed for indication the general level of employee satisfaction.

Statement of the Problem:

There is evidence to suggest that job satisfaction can influence job performance and vice versa. A satisfied employee may be more motivated, engaged, and committed to their work, potentially leading to higher job performance. Conversely, high job performance can contribute to job satisfaction through increased self-esteem, recognition, and career advancement. Several factors can mediate the relationship between job satisfaction and job performance. For example, organizational factors like leadership, work environment, and company culture can influence both job satisfaction and performance outcomes. Individual differences such as personality traits, values, and personal goals can moderate how job satisfaction translates into job performance. For instance, a person with high job satisfaction may still perform poorly if they lack the necessary skills or face organizational barriers. Both job satisfaction and job performance are multifaceted constructs that can be measured in various ways. Researchers often use self-report surveys for job satisfaction and objective measures (like sales figures, productivity metrics) or supervisor ratings for job performance. High job satisfaction and job performance are generally associated with positive organizational outcomes such as lower turnover rates, higher employee morale, and increased productivity. The causality between job satisfaction and job performance is debated in research. While some studies indicate a stronger effect of job satisfaction on performance, others suggest that performance can lead to increased job satisfaction. While a positive relationship between job satisfaction and job performance is widely acknowledged, the exact nature and strength of this relationship can vary based on individual, organizational, and contextual factors. Organizations often aim to enhance both job satisfaction and job performance through various strategies such as improving working conditions, providing developmental opportunities, and fostering a supportive work environment. Therefore the problem stated here is “Role of job Performance on the Job Satisfaction: A Study on the Elementary School Teachers”.

Significance of the study:

Elementary school teachers play a pivotal role in shaping educational experiences and outcomes for young students. Their job satisfaction can directly impact their teaching effectiveness, which in turn affects student engagement, learning outcomes, and overall educational quality. Job satisfaction significantly influences teacher retention rates. Understanding how job performance contributes to job satisfaction can provide insights into strategies to improve teacher retention, reduce turnover, and maintain continuity in educational environments. Schools function as organizations where effective performance of teachers contributes to the overall effectiveness of the institution. Job satisfaction among teachers is linked to factors such as morale, collaboration, and commitment, which are crucial for a positive organizational climate. Findings from such studies can inform educational policies and management practices. For instance, identifying factors that enhance job performance and satisfaction can guide interventions in professional development, workload

management, leadership practices, and resource allocation within schools. Job satisfaction impacts the personal and professional well-being of teachers. Higher job satisfaction is associated with lower stress levels, better mental health, and greater job commitment, all of which contribute to a healthier and more stable workforce in education.

Objectives:

This study examines the relationship between job performance and job satisfaction among elementary school teachers. It also examines the impact of job satisfaction on the job performance.

Methodology:

Research Design: Descriptive Survey research design has been applied in the current study.

Population and Sample:

Population for the current study comprised of the Elementary school teachers working the district of Paschim Medinipur, West Bengal. Out of the existing population the researcher has selected a sample of 150 Elementary school teachers by following the purposive sampling method for collecting the primary data.

Tools: In order to gauge how well people were doing their jobs, a teacher-made work performance scale was created. School teachers' job descriptions and responsibilities informed the development of the fifteen statements that made up the performance scale. Total scores may be anywhere from 0 to 60 on the five-point scale that went from very good to very bad, with individual scores of 4, 3, 2, 1, and 0 corresponding to each of the four categories.

Another structured questionnaire consisting of 20 statements was used for measuring the job satisfaction level of the Elementary school teachers.

Statistical Techniques: Collected data were tabulated and analyzed in the SPSS version 20 by applying the descriptive statistics and t test.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of Job Performance among Elementary School Teachers

Parameters	Values
N	150
Minimum	18
Maximum	56
Mean	35.86
Range	38
Median	35
Standard Deviation	9.96
SEM	0.81
Skewness	0.16
Kurtosis	2.10

The dataset consists of 150 observations ranging from 18 to 56. The data has a mean of 35.86 and a median of 35, indicating a roughly symmetric distribution with a slight right skewness. The standard deviation of 9.96 shows moderate variability in the dataset. The kurtosis of 2.10 indicates moderate peakedness compared to a normal distribution. The standard error of the mean (SEM) of 0.81 suggests that the sample mean is expected to vary by approximately 0.81 units from the true population mean. The mean value is higher than the midpoint of the data sheet which clearly indicates that Elementary school teachers have higher job performance.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics of Job Satisfaction among Elementary School Teachers

Parameters	Values
N	150
Minimum	22
Maximum	75
Mean	44.53
Range	53
Median	45
Standard Deviation	14.35
SEM	1.17
Skewness	0.29
Kurtosis	2.17

The data is based on a sample of 150 observations. The scores range from 22 to 75, with an average score (mean) of 44.53 and a median of 45. This suggests that the data distribution is approximately symmetric. The standard deviation of 14.35 indicates moderate variability in the scores around the mean. The skewness of 0.29 indicates a slight right skew, meaning there are slightly more scores on the higher end of the range. The kurtosis of 2.17 indicates that the distribution is platykurtic, with slightly lighter tails compared to a normal distribution. The mean value is higher than the midpoint of the data sheet. Therefore it can be concluded that the job satisfaction among elementary school teachers is high.

Table 3: Impact of Job Satisfaction on the Job Performance

Source	DF	Sum of Square	Mean Square	F Statistic	P Value
between groups	1	5200.0025	5200.00	34.07	1.38e-8
Within Groups	298	45471.9277	152.59		
Total	299	50671.9302	169.47		

The F statistic (34.07) compares the variability between groups to the variability within groups. A larger F statistic suggests a greater difference between group means relative to the variability within groups. The extremely small p-value (1.38e-8) associated with the between-groups variation indicates that there is strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis. In other words, the differences between the groups are statistically significant. Therefore, there is evidence to suggest that the factor being tested (such as different treatments or conditions) has a significant effect on the outcome variable, as it explains a significant amount of the variability in the data compared to what would be expected by chance.

Table 4: Relationship between Job satisfaction and job Performance

Parameter	Value
Pearson correlation coefficient (r)	0.05
r^2	0.003265
P-value	0.4874
Covariance	8.1642
Sample size (n)	150
Statistic	0.6963

The Pearson correlation coefficient (r) of 0.05 suggests a very weak positive linear relationship between the variables. However, this relationship is so weak that it is likely not practically significant. The r^2 value of 0.003265 indicates that only a very small proportion (about 0.33%) of the variability in one variable can be attributed to the variability in the other variable. The high p-value of 0.4874 (> 0.05) indicates that there is no statistically significant correlation between the

variables at the 5% significance level. The covariance of 8.1642 shows the direction of the relationship between the variables (positive covariance), but it does not indicate the strength of the relationship as clearly as the correlation coefficient does.

Findings: The following have been found from the data analysis-

1. Job Satisfaction among Elementary School Teachers is high.
2. Job Performance among Elementary School Teachers is high.
3. Job satisfaction has significant impact on the job performance among elementary school teachers.
4. There is a weak positive linear relationship between Job Satisfaction and the Job Performance

Conclusion:

In conclusion, this study underscores the significance of job performance in shaping job satisfaction among elementary school teachers. By enhancing job performance metrics and addressing factors that contribute to satisfaction, educational institutions can create supportive environments that promote teacher well-being and improve overall educational outcomes.

References

1. Ali, N. & Z. (2009). Job Status, Gender and Level of Education as Determinants of Satisfaction of Senior Secondary School Teachers . *Indian Journal of Social Science Researchers* . 6 (1), pp. 56-59.
2. Alina Bota, O. (2013). Researches ‘ Job satisfaction of teachers ’ 2nd World Conference on Educational Technology.83, pp. 634 – 638.
3. Bharti (2005), ‘Comparative study of job Satisfaction of Government and Private School teachers at Secondary level’’, C.C.S. University Meerut.
4. George, S & K J (2011). ‘ A study on job satisfaction of employees in bpcl – kochi refinery limited, ambalamugal’ Christ University, National Conference on Emerging Trends in Business, pp.1-12 .
5. Ibrahim, A., Al-Taneiji, S.: (2019)Teacher satisfaction in Abu Dhabi public schools: what the numbers did not say. *Issues Educ. Res.* **29**(1), 106–122.
6. Khatoon, M.& T. (2012). ‘ Demographic differences and Occupational Stress of secondary school teachers ’ *European Scientific Journal* . 8(5).
7. Martin, L.E. (2005).’Job satisfaction of secondary school teachers National’ *Distance Education University* 33(2), pp. 435-452. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.6018/rie.33.2.202841>.
8. Mishra S and R.N. Tripathi (2002), ‘ Predicting job satisfaction organizational effectiveness and leadership styles in public and private sector organization. *Behavioural Scientist* 3(1), 13 P.P.
9. Rasto, R., (2019)Yulianti Maulani, S.: Satisfaction and motivation as determinants of teacher performance. *Jurnal Pendidikan Bisnis dan Manajemen* 5(1), 11–21 .
10. Selvabaskar.S, Surulivel.S. T, Alamelu & Nigama.K.(2018). Job satisfaction among school teachers” *India International journal of pure and applied mathematics school of management, sastra deemed university Thirumalaisamudram, Thanjavur, Tamilnadu, volume 119 No. 7 2018, pp. 2645- 2655 ISSN: 1311-8080.*
11. Sivakumar, S.A. (2019). ‘ Job satisfaction among school teachers in Coimbatore district’, *zenith International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*. pp. 134-141.
12. Singh, Gurmit (2007). Job Satisfaction of Teacher Educators in Relation to their Attitude towards Teaching. Retrieved from http://www.aiaer.net/journal/vol.19207/25._Gurmit_Singh.htm. on 02/03/2009.